

Canada Passes National *Pharmacare Act*

Issue/problem

On [October 10, 2024](#), Canada passed Bill C-64, also known as the [Pharmacare Act](#), marking a significant step towards a universal, single-payer pharmacare system. This bill provides a framework to make prescription drugs accessible to all Canadians, allowing the federal government to enter into agreements with the provinces and territories to cover the cost of drugs, starting eligibility with coverage for diabetes treatments and contraceptives.

Description of the problem

While the *Act's* framework represents a first step to providing universal pharmacare to Canadians, political and economic obstacles remain. Its implementation hinges on agreements yet to be negotiated with provincial and territorial governments. However, Health Minister Mark Holland hopes to have agreements in place by the [spring of 2025](#). While some provinces, including [British Columbia](#), have already indicated interest in moving quickly, others, including [Alberta](#), have expressed opposition to the program based on its duplication of provincial programs and concerns about federal overreach. Further, Conservative Party leader Pierre Poilievre [stated his intention](#) to scrap any single-payer drug plan, arguing that such a plan would eliminate private drug plans and affect existing coverage.

Results

The Canadian government estimates that the *Act* will provide universal access to medication for [3.7 million people](#) living with diabetes and various forms of contraception [to more than 9 million people](#) of reproductive age.

Lessons learned

The impact of the nascent program on the Canadian pharmaceutical market remains difficult to ascertain. While the legislation refers to a single-payer system, in which governments would have the exclusive ability to negotiate drug prices with manufacturers, the *Act's* initial limited scope means that it will not replace existing provincial and private drug coverage. The [Parliamentary Budget Office](#) estimates that the first phase of coverage of contraception and diabetic treatments will cost \$1.9 billion over five years. The next federal election, which must occur on or before October 20, 2025, could result in the program's cancellation, as Poilievre's Conservatives are [currently polling at a 22% lead](#) over the governing Liberals.